

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№9

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 950 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-sentyabrda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Postdan xaridgacha: influenser va ilg'or veb-ilova (PWA – progressive web app)ning chakana sotuvga real ta'siri	14
Abdulaziz Madjidov	
Ta'lim xizmatlari bozori samaradorligini oshirishda ta'lim klasterlarining roli	22
Imamova Nilufar Asamutdinovna	
Korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketingning tovar strategiyasidan foydalanish holati.....	29
Xidirov Sherzod Olimovich	
O'zbekistonda moliyaviy savodxonlikni institutsionallashtirish: NFIS, Finlit.uz va ta'lim islohotlari	34
Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	
Moslashuvchan menejment tizimlarini yashil iqtisodiyotga integratsiyalash tasnifi	39
Umarov Bezzod Batirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion marketing strategiyasini ishlab chiqish.....	43
Sheraliev Axror Sodiqovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida moliyaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tendensiyalari, undan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari va konseptual jihatlari	48
Roziqov Behzod Bahrom o'g'li	
Metallurgiya korxonalarida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish chet el tajribasi	54
Abdullayeva Matluba Nematovna	
Исследование связи между восприятием изменения климата и внедрением устойчивых методов ведения сельского хозяйства в Узбекистане	59
Светлана Ражабова, Бахром Миркасимов	
Surxondaryo viloyati qishloq xo'jalik tarmog'ini barqaror rivojlantirishni iqtisodiy-ekologik modellari	68
Abdug'aniyev Otobek Allajonovich, Xo'jamqulov Bekzod Turdaliyevich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda real sektor salmog'i va uning o'zgarish tendensiyalari	75
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdievich, Isoilova Muhabbat Rustamjon qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymatni soliqqa tortish uslubiyoti: xususiyatlari, vazifalari va muammolari	89
Xaitov Shuxrat Sharipboyevich	
Kognitiv yondashuv asosida tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari grammatik va diskursiv kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy modeli va pedagogik texnologiyasi.....	94
Dadadjanova Feruza Muhammadyusupovna	
Transport tizimining rivojlanishi milliy iqtisodiy o'sishining asosi sifatida	98
Narziyev Umidjon Baxrillayevich	
Loyiha risklarini aniqlashda zamonaviy usullar va ularning samaradorligi.....	105
Marufhanov Davron Xasanovich	
Современные методы управления на железнодорожном транспорте в процессе трансформации системы.....	109
Кушакова Мамура Наримановна	
Финансовые механизмы и модели менеджмента в развитии устойчивой экономики транспортных компаний	115
Шарапова Гулчебра Рустамовна	
Kasbiy ta'limda o'quvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va baholashning innovatsion yondashuvlari	120
Maxkamova Zuhra Tursunpulotovna	
Audit ishi sifati darajasini oshirish yo'nalishlari.....	124
Qushmatov Otaxon Qurbonaliyevich	

Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari.....	131
Yuldashev Baxtiyor Gayradjonovich	
Ko'chmas mulk qiymatini baholash va uning ekonometrik tahlili	135
Jaloliddinova Mohira Alisher qizi	
Современные тенденции и вызовы бюджетно-макроэкономической политики в Узбекистане	142
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
Интеллектуал mulkda iqtisodiy mohiyat, mazmun hamda huquqiy jihat uyg'unligi	148
N.D.Maxmudova	
Axborot texnologiyalari asosida ta'limda loyiha boshqaruvida sun'iy intellekt va mashinali o'qitish imkoniyatlari	152
Xodjiyeva Durdona Abdurasolovna	
Концепция "Зеленого учета" и его значение для экономического развития.....	157
Умарова Зулайхо Турсуновна	
Iqtisodiyotning asosiy tarmoq va sohalariga kiritilgan investitsiyalarning joriy holati tahlili	166
Ismailova Kutlibeka Ulug'bek qizi	
O'zbekistonda yoshlar tashkiloti faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos jihatlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	172
Usmonov Adxamjon A'zamjonovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maxsus iqtisodiy zonalarini investitsion holatini hududlar kesimida tahlili.....	178
Anvarxonov Abdulatifxon Jamshidxon o'g'li	
Kichik biznes va o'rta biznesni rivojlantirish orqali aholi farovonligini ta'minlash.....	184
Ahmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich, Nurqulov Nurbek Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Fiskal siyosat instrumentlari orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni qisqartirish va legallashtirish metodologiyasi.....	189
Ergasheva Malikaxon Avazxon qizi	
Fond bozorida savdo strategiyasi va uni amalga oshirishga yo'nalishlari.....	192
Soliyev Istam Ixtiyorovich	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion rivojlantirishning asosiy tamoyillari	197
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda davlat boshqaruvi tizimining isloh qilinishi: Tajriba va istiqbollar.....	202
Mashrabaliyev Ibroximbek Mashrabaliyevich	
Iqtisodiyotning real sektorida investitsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirish amaliyoti.....	209
Qosimova Lola Sultanovna	
Sanoat mahsulotlari eksportida logistika zanjirining uzluksizligini ta'minlash: nazariy asoslar va amaliy yondashuvlar.....	217
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdulkarim qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali qo'shilgan qiymat soliq ma'murchiligi bazasini kengaytirish yo'llari	222
Raxmonqulov Umidjon Rustam o'g'li	
Инновационные подходы к созданию проблемно-ориентированной системы прогнозирования, оптимизации и управления отраслями региональной экономики (жилищное строительство)	231
Далиев Ахтам Шарафутдинович	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati samaradorligini oshirishda UZEX faoliyatining joriy holatini baholash.....	238
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Mamatkulov Farrux Gulomjon o'g'li	
Sog'liqni saqlash tizimida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining turlari	244
Solikhova Dildora Alisher qizi	

“O‘ztemiryo‘lyo‘lovchi” ajning asisiiy faoliyatini samaradorligini oshirishda autsorsing xizmatini joriy etish strategik asoslari	250
Kaxarova Nilufar Yerkinjonovna	
Mintaqani kompleks rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ustuvor yo‘nalishlari.....	256
Jumayeva Zulfiya Qayumovna	
Sog‘liqni saqlash tashkilotarida xarajatlar samaradorligini ta‘minlash masalalari	260
Raximova Maftuna Axmadjon qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida sof foydani taqsimlash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan soliq solish masalalari.....	264
Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston qonunchiligida raqamli transformatsiya jarayonida elektron to‘lov kartalarini soxtalashtirishni jinoyatlashtirish.....	276
Maxsadaliyeva Maftuna Toxir qizi	
Mamlakatimizda intellektual xizmatlar bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	281
Miyassarov Davron Abdurashid o‘g‘li	
Validation of the dutch eating behaviour questionnaire (DEBQ) in a sample of uzbek women.....	285
Khursana Usmanova, Dr Muhammad Bilal, Dilafuz Qo‘chqorova	
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlik tizimlarini o‘ziga xos jihatlari	295
Nabiyev Bexzod Shavkatovich, Bayboboeva Firuza Nabijonovna	
Davlat qarz siyosatini optimallashtirishda islomiy moliya instrumentlarining qo‘llanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish yo‘nalishlari	299
Tilabov Nasrulla Tashmurotovich	
Роль институциональных структур фондового рынка в обеспечении финансовой стабильности.....	305
Камилова Севара Анваровна	
The Impact of Digitalization on the Management System in the Entrepreneurial Environment of Uzbekistan.....	309
Ibragimova Saida Ilkhomovna	
China’s Investment Strategy in Uzbekistan: Sectoral Trends and Strategic Implications (2013–2024).....	313
Maftuna Nuriddinova	
Qo‘shilgan qiymat solig‘i tushunchasi va uning iqtisodiy mohiyati	319
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
Raqamli boshqaruvning afzalliklari va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	324
Xolbayeva Marg‘uba Qazoqboyevna	
Korporativ boshqaruvning nazariy asoslari: O‘zbekistonda qo‘llanish imkoniyatlari.....	328
Jumayeva Guzal Sherxon qizi	
Audit organizations in Uzbekistan	332
Razzaqov Jasur Xamraboevich, Yaqubov Matrasul Mavlonberdiyevich, Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarning turlari va xususiyatlari	337
Gofurov Doston Boxromovich	
Mahalliy budjet mablag‘larining samaradorligini oshirishda auditning o‘rni.....	341
Primova Shaxnoza Komiljonovna	
Модели управления государственными финансами в зарубежных странах.....	345
Наимов Шохрух Шарофиддинович	
O‘zbekistonning sirkulyar iqtisodiyotga o‘tishi: yashil o‘sinh indikatorlari tahlili	352
Hakimov Anvarjon Abdulloyevich	
Innovation management in the education system: practical challenges, international experience, and effective strategies based on the example of Uzbekistan.....	356
Imomov Inomiddin Abdulxamidovich, Egamberdiyev Farxod Botirovich	
Трансформация энергетического комплекса Узбекистана: текущее состояние и перспективы развития	363
Хмель Е.В., Мирджалилова Д.Ш., Дерюгина Е.А., Лозовская Н.А.	

Improving the efficiency of personnel management and optimizing labor costs in Sam Glass LLC.....	368
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Interactive design and museum management: enhancing guided tours through IOT and virtual solutions.....	374
Ibrokhimova Aziza Abbasovna	
Hududlar investitsion jozibadorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	379
Imomova Kamola Novfal qizi	
“Innovatsion usulda baliq yetishtirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari (Sirdaryo tumani misolida)”	385
Bo'ltakov Sardor Oqbo'ta o'g'li	
Bank filial tarmoqlari samaradorligini baholashning xorijiy tajribasi va undan O'zbekiston banklari amaliyotida foydalanish imkoniyatlari	392
Xoshimov Og'abek Nizomjon o'g'li	
Zamonaviy iqtisodiyotda davlat xaridlarinin elektron savdolarning o'rni	398
Burxanov G'ofur Baxodirovich	
Реализация концепции развития рынка зеленой экономики в сфере экономической безопасности Республики Узбекистан.....	401
Юнусова Римма Рахманбердиевна	
Tijorat banklaridan “foйда” solig'ini undirishning bugungi holati.....	408
Ergasheva Lobar Raxmatulla qizi	
O'zbekiston oziq-ovqat sanoatini iqtisodiy rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	415
Abasova Gulirano Rahmatullo qizi	
Xorijiy tajribalar asosida ekologik tadbirkorlikning innovatsion va investitsion yo'nalishlarini tashkil etish	419
Turg'unova Tursunoy Maratovna	
Sanoat korxonalarini jozibadorligini oshirishda marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish xususiyatlari	424
Raxmonova Feruza Musakulovna	
Turizm sohasida investitsion faoliyat: nazariy asoslar va amaliy yo'nalishlar.....	428
Ergashev Durdonaxon Aziz qizi	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida barqaror turizmning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va mavjud muammolar tahlili.....	432
Suyunova Dilnoza Mexridin qizi	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish jarayonida investitsion resurslarning mutanosib taqsimlanishi: samaradorlik va ustuvor yo'nalishlar.....	436
Otaboyev Feruzbek Oybek o'g'li	
Xususiy banklar faoliyatini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning moliya bozoriga ta'siri	441
Abduqahhorov Asilbek Ahror o'g'li	
Mehnat resurslari tushunchasi, tarkibi va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	447
Kobilova Zebo Bobokulovna	
Xorijiy davlatlar tajribasida moliyaviy siyosatning makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi roli.....	453
Jabborova Dilafuz	
The impact of exchange rate policy on the financial-monetary system and economic growth.....	459
Raxmanova Laylo Baxodirovna	
Современные вызовы и модельные подходы к обеспечению конкурентоспособности банковской системы Узбекистана.....	464
Юлдашева С.Ш.	
Iqtisodiyotni innovatsion rivojlantirishda soliq mexanizmidan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	470
Ishimova Mohinur Absalomovna	
Innovative pathways for advancing sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan.....	477
Feruz Karimov	

Tijorat banklarida biznes subyektlari faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	482
Mirpulatova Luiza Mansurovna	
O'zbekistonda sanoat zonalarining rivojlanish bosqichlari va huquqiy-me'yoriy asoslari	488
Vafojev Akmal Ikromovich	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan samarali foydalanishda Germaniya tajribasi	493
Pardayeva Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi	
Korxonalar moliyaviy faoliyati bo'yicha auditorlik risklarini xalqaro standartlar asosida baholash	497
Shirinov Uchqun Abduxalilovich, Abduxalil-zoda Ra'no Muzaffar qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining tarkibi va ularni pasaytirish usullari	501
Sodiqov Mirahror Abbos o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda mahalliy budjetlarning ahamiyati.....	509
Sharopov Dilshodjon Raxmatullayevich	
The role of small business enterprises in enhancing the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan	513
Djalilova Shaxlo Ismoiljon kizi	
O'zbekistonda IPOlarni tashkil etish jarayonlari tahlili	518
Alikulov Azamat Tuygunovich	
Kichik sanoat zonalarini faoliyatining iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	522
Ozoda Batirovna Sakiyeva	
Hududlarning innovatsion turistik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	528
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
Integrating circular economy principles in marketing and operations of grape export companies for green transition.....	534
Usmonova Diyora Mahmud kizi	
Foreign experiences of improving the quality of services in the field of tourism.....	541
Raxmonov Siyovush Turob ugli	
Z avlodining iste'dodli vakillari uchun raqobat: davlat boshqaruvi sektorining maqsadga yo'naltirilgan raqamli avlodni jalb etish strategiyalari.....	546
Nosirova Shaxzoda Bohodir qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida uglerod solig'ini joriy etish orqali soliq ma'muriyatchiligini takomillashtirish va yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishni jadallashtirish imkoniyatlari: ekologik, iqtisodiy va institutsional yondashuv	560
Jo'rayev Ahmad Saitnazar o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari reytingiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar tahlili.....	566
Karabayev Nodir Abduhamidovich	
Budjet tashkilotlarida tuziladigan moliyaviy hisobotlarning ahamiyati.....	578
Norqulova Qutlug'nigor Oloviddinovna	
Методы и критерии оценки эффективности конкурентоспособности предприятия	582
Хусейнов Рахим Али оглы	
Zamonaviy HR texnologiyalarining korxonalar samaradorligiga ta'siri: "O'zbekiston temir yo'llari" AJ tajribasi.....	589
Xursanova Gulshan Ravshan qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida innovatsion menejment strategiyalarining samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	593
Pulatova Dildora Abdushukurovna	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llashning bugungi kunda o'rni va ahamiyati.....	600
Xolmirzayeva Gulruxsor Maxammetovna	
Интеграция информационно-коммуникационных технологий в зеленую экономику: цифровые технологии для устойчивого развития.....	604
Бозорова Ирина Жуманазаровна	

Xorijiy mamlakatlarda tadbirkorlik subyektlari tomonidan mahalliyashtirish asosida mahsulot ishlab chiqarishning o'ziga xos jihatlari	608
Mirzabaev Xusniddin Muxamadjonovich	
Цифровизация зеленой экономики: синергия технологий для устойчивого будущего	616
Мухамадиева Кибриё Баходировна, Умарова Надира Рахмановна, Шарипова Зулфия Шокиржоновна, Эшпулатова Хусния Мирғолиб кизи	
O'zbekistonda to'qimachilik mahsulotlari bozori va rivojlanishi	621
Alimxodjayeva Nargiza Elshodovna	
Samarqand viloyatida tikuv-to'qimachilik sanoatining rivojlanish holati va ishlab chiqarish hajmining prognozi.....	629
Ikramova Taxmina Latifovna	
Повышение эффективности управления рисками в проектах государственно-частного партнерства в сфере услуг	639
Айтбаева Гульзада Куанышбаевна	
Surxondaryo viloyati iqtisodiy o'sish darajalarini ekonometrik modellashtirish	645
Pardayeva Ma'rifat Muzaffarovna	
Зарубежный опыт развития экономики ресурсно-сырьевых регионов: модели диверсификации и возможности адаптации.....	654
Севара Кахрамоновна Хакбердиева	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishning ahamiyati.....	658
Abduvoxidova Mohinur Akmalovna	
O'zbekiston sug'urta bozorida esg va yashil moliya instrumentlaridan foydalanish holati va imkoniyatlari.....	662
Zoyirov Laziz Subxonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida transport xizmatlari ko'rsatishning amaldagi holati tahlili va uni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	668
Sharipova Bibijon Baxtiyorovna	
Ulgurji savdo qoidalari va chakana savdodan farqli tomonlari	678
Batirova Raxima Abdujabbarovna, Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
Xalqaro integratsiya jarayonlarida raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'rni.....	684
Zaripov Xurshid Zakir o'g'li	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromadlari va xarajatlarining hozirgi holati	690
Himmatov Abdisamat Xalilovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida aholining moliyaviy madaniyatini rivojlantirish muammolari va istiqbollari.....	696
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibayevna	
Цели устойчивого развития и роль цифровых платформ в сфере трудовой миграции	702
Газиёва Сулхия Саидмашрафовна	
Onlayn savdo maydonchalarida mijoz sodiqligini shakllantirishda marketing strategiyalarining o'rni.....	706
Vaxromov Xudoyor Xabibullo o'g'li	
Методологические основы оценки эффективности «зеленых» технологий в строительном секторе.....	710
Тожиева Дилфуза Бабамуратовна	
Korxonalarda moliyaviy instrumentlar auditi masalalarini rivojlantirish.....	715
Mahmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi soliq ma'murchiligini takomillashtirish jarayonlari	722
Mahmudova Sevara Rahmat qizi, Alardonov Muxammadali Ibragimovich	
Improving the efficiency of modern housing fund management system	726
D.A. Berdiyeva, Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
Kichik va o'rta biznes subyektlari eksport salohiyatini rivojlantirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish	731
Abduqahhorov Azizbek Abdullo o'g'li	

From Science to Business: How Universities Stimulate Innovation.....	735
A. Bobozhonov, A.M. Shatre, V. Kirilova Vladimirova, R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
Tashkilotlarda risklarni boshqarish strategiyalarining samaradorligini baholash: nazariy va amaliy yondashuvlar	740
Husanova Dilnura Mamrajab qizi	
Turli mulkchilik shakllaridagi xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar faoliyatining ekologik auditining nazariy jihatlarini	744
Abdullayev Xurshidjon Nazrullo o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish omillari.....	749
Ne'matullayev Abdurasulxon Ximaydulla o'g'li	
Bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish sharoitida innovatsion korxonalar boshqaruvi tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi amal qilish xususiyatlari	755
Naimov Azamat Xikmatovich	
Mamlakatimizda chet el investitsiyasi ishtirokidagi korxonalar faoliyatini rivojlantirish.....	758
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Shuxratov Azizbek A'zamjon o'g'li	
Quritilgan organik mevalar eksportini rivojlantirishda yashil marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish.....	764
Xidirov Shohrux Bobir o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmatlar sohasining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari.....	769
Ernazarov Gulam Bekbayevich	
Kichik biznes subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni baholash va rivojlantirish mexanizmlari.....	774
Mavulov Ravshan Nematjonovich	
Barqaror rivojlanish va korxonalarda barqarorlikni ta'minlash zaruriyati.....	780
Yakubova Dilfuza	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitlarida barqaror rivojlanish, yashil texnologiyalar va ekologik menejmentning o'rni	785
Dilmurodov Abbas Anvar o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi sohasi faoliyatini davlat tomonidan muvofiqlashtirish va boshqarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	788
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
Tijorat banklarida chakana bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirish.....	795
Axmedov G'ofurjon G'ulomjonovich	
Turizm sohasini ekonometrik modellashtirishda qo'llaniladigan ekonometrik usullar va amaliy imkoniyatlar	801
Shukurov Ikrom Abdurashitovich	
Sanoat tarmoqlarida investitsiyalar strukturasi iqtisodiy samaradorligi va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish.....	807
Xikmatillayeva Dildora Shavkat qizi	
Mintaqa ziyorat turizmi samaradorligini oshirishda ekonometrik modellardan foydalanish.....	812
O'rinova Durdona Botir qizi	
Kichik biznes rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni pest (siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy-demografik, texnologik omillar) tahlili.....	816
Israilov Rustam Ibragimovich	
Qazib olish sanoati korxonalarini moliyaviy sog'lomlashtirishda muammolar va salbiy omillar: tahlil va zamonaviy yondashuvlar	825
Abduraxmanov Davron Burxanjonovich	
O'zbekistonning milliy merosi boyliklaridan turizmga foydalanish yo'llari	830
Samarov Xonqul Qahhorovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish jarayonida investision resurslarning mutanosib taqsimlanishi: samaradorlik va ustuvor yo'nalishlar	835
Otaboyev Feruzbek Oybek o'g'li	
Iqtisodiyotning ekologik transformatsiyasi sharoitida ijtimoiy o'sishni indikativ baholash metodologiyasi.....	841
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o'g'li	

Bojxona xizmati fiskal faoliyatini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	847
Pardayev To'liqin Nasirovich, Farxodov Farrux Furqatovich, Nomozov Abduvoxid bdurazzoq o'g'li	
Механизмы устойчивого управления малым и средним бизнесом в условиях цифровизации и внедрения искусственного интеллекта.....	852
Зокирова Фарангиз Тулкиновна	
Yashil bank xizmatlari va uni joriy etish bilan bog'liq muammolar.....	862
Makhmudova Mukhlisa Kodirjon kizi	
Barqaror qishloq xo'jaligi ta'minot zanjirlarida transport tizimlarini optimallashtirish.....	867
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Moliyaviy rejalashtirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mazmuni	874
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
Mintaqa sanoatida kichik biznesni qo'llab-quvvatlash va infratuzilmasini tashkil etish.....	881
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida 2010–2024-yillardagi yalpi hududiy mahsulotining iqtisodiy statistik tahlili.....	888
Ismoilov Davronbek Iloxomjon o'g'li	
Yashil obligatsiyalar va barqaror moliyalashtirishning davlat qarzi siyosatiga ta'siri.....	893
Tilabov Nasrulla Tashmurotovich	
Модели Альтмана и Таффлера как инструмент диагностики финансовой устойчивости предприятий.....	897
Утемуратова Бибиixon Даниловна	
Individual tadbirkorlik va mustaqil bandlik asosida olinadigan daromadlarni soliqqa tortishning fundamental asoslari	903
Yakubov San'abek Ravshanbekovich	
China's trade relations with Central Asia: an empirical analysis based on the trade gravity model.....	912
Ye Maoqing	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasida smart texnologiyalar joriy etishning holati va yo'nalishlari.....	920
Qutfiddinov Shamsiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	
Application of modern information systems in the assessment of the technical condition of the equipment of electrical energy networks.....	924
Sobirov Muzaffar Azatovich	
Стратегическое управление экономическим потенциалом Узбекистана.....	932
Садуллаева Муслимахон Саидамировна	
Auditda raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash tarixi va istiqbollari	936
Muydinov Erkin Djamaldinovich	
Bank majburiyatlari va aktivlarining vaqtinchalik nomutanosibliklari riskini kamaytirish.....	940
Ibrohimov D.M.	
Priority directions and legal bases of improving of the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.....	945
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	

potential violations, but also to quickly respond to changing conditions of tax legislation and the economic situation. Let's look at the main components and capabilities of this solution:

- Data collection and integration. The CRM system aggregates information from various sources: accounting data, tax returns, registers, and external information systems. This allows you to create a single database for further analysis and assessment of tax risks. This approach ensures transparency of processes and simplifies document flow at all stages of working with tax information.

- Assessment and classification of tax risks. The system is based on analytical tools that use machine learning algorithms and Big Data methods to identify anomalies, correlations, and trends. This helps to divide taxpayers into groups based on the level of risk (high, medium, low) and to identify potentially problematic areas that require additional monitoring or corrective measures in a timely manner.

- Real-time monitoring and analytical dashboards. The system generates dashboards with key risk indicators, dynamics of changes and trends in tax revenues, which allows managers and tax authorities to quickly make decisions. Automated notifications and alerts allow you not to miss critical moments associated with exceeding risk thresholds.

- Managing processes and making corrective decisions. Based on the obtained data, the CRM system helps you plan and initiate measures to reduce tax risks. This may include adjusting accounting policies, reallocating resources to conduct targeted audits, and developing recommendations for improving tax control processes. In addition, the system can integrate with ERP and other business platforms, which provides a systematic approach to managing tax liabilities.

- Ensuring information security and compliance with regulatory requirements. To protect confidential information, the system uses state-of-the-art access controls, data encryption, and electronic signatures. This guarantees the legal validity of documents and complies with modern security standards for processing sensitive information.

- Flexibility and scalability. Integrated tax risk management systems easily adapt to changes in legislation and industry requirements, which is especially important in a dynamically changing economic environment. The ability to scale allows implementing such solutions both at the level of individual companies and within the framework of national tax control digitalization programs [2].

In Uzbekistan, such CRM systems are integrated into the overall strategy of digitalization of tax accounting and control, helping to increase the transparency of tax processes, reduce operational risks and improve interaction between tax authorities and taxpayers [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In their scientific research, Professor F. Mirzaev, Professor F. Isaev and Associate Professor U. Berdieva conducted in-depth research on the issues of modernizing the tax system in particular [8], tax collection and raising its level, and Professor S. Giyasov analyzed the problems of reducing tax arrears and mandatory payments in his scientific works. Scientific research in this area was also carried out by N. Kurbankulova, and M. Elbayeva investigated the problems of determining tax risk. However, although these scientific studies have conducted separate studies of some tax indicators, comprehensive scientific studies of the relationship between tax risk, tax arrears and tax collection in an automated tax system have not been conducted. In this regard, in the conditions of the New Uzbekistan, there is still a need to conduct scientific research on the relationship between tax debt and tax collection with automation and the choice of evaluation criteria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

When conducting research on the prospects for studying the tax system in the period of globalization, we used data analysis methods, where the basis is the collection and study of statistical data (tax revenues, GDP, employment rate, number of taxpayers), analyzed the dynamics of changes in tax indicators for the 2021-2024 tax period. Official data includes the Tax Code, government regulations, open databases (statistical reports of the Ministry of Economy and Finance, reports of Tax authorities), scientific publications and research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Before presenting the problems of the tax system and possible prospects, it is necessary to study the automated tax system. An automated system is a permit system that gives the right to work with software products and automated information systems, and is implemented in a single integrated information database of the State Tax Service. To access the automated system, a username and passwords are provided in accordance with the information security requirements. Through automated systems, you can grant access to all systems owned by the user. Automated systems are divided into all levels, and the systems in it are grouped [8].

1. The automated workplace of the tax inspector-5 (SOARJ-5) is intended for keeping records of NPYULS and their tax liabilities, as well as personal accounts.

2. With the help of the Bank DSK information system, you can track daily receipts to budget and extra-budgetary funds online. The main purpose and task of the information system 1-H is to record the daily revenues of the budget system and ensure control over the implementation of specified forecast indicators.

The Bank DSK information system is a complete solution designed to automate and optimize the bank's main business processes. It integrates various business lines into a single platform that allows you to quickly access up-to-date data and make operational management decisions.

3. The automated lease agreement accounting system is a tool that allows you to manage lease agreements in a comprehensive manner, simplifying document flow and reducing the risk of errors when working with them. The main features of such a system include:

Centralized storage and organization of documents. The system provides storage of all contracts in electronic form, which allows you to quickly find the necessary documents, catalog them by various filters (date of conclusion, validity period, object type, etc.) and maintain a single archive of information.

Automated management of contract deadlines. Integrated reminders and notifications help you monitor the end dates, renewals, or renegotiations of your contracts. This prevents delinquency and allows you to prepare the necessary measures for updating the lease relationship in a timely manner.

Integration with accounting and financial accounting. The system automatically communicates with accounting solutions, allowing you to calculate rent, track actual receipts, monitor overdue payments, and generate financial statements. This functionality reduces the risk of errors, speeds up data processing, and promotes transparency.

Support for the contract lifecycle. From creating contract templates, preparing them, approving them, approving them, and editing them, to archiving them – all stages can be optimized within a single platform. This allows you to automate the workflow and saves employees from routine tasks.

Integration with CRM and ERP systems. The ability to link the contract accounting system with customer relationship management solutions and corporate resources ensures synchronization of data across objects, reduces duplication of information, and simplifies work planning.

Ensuring information security. The use of state-of-the-art data protection standards, role-based access differentiation, and digital signature support guarantee reliable contract storage and processing, as well as compliance with regulatory requirements [3].

Generate analytical reports and monitor them. The system can automatically generate reports on the status of contracts, revenue dynamics, and other key indicators, which helps you evaluate the effectiveness of working with rental relationships and make informed management decisions.

In 2024, 606 thousand lease agreements were registered with the tax authorities. 799.5 billion soums of taxes were accrued under these agreements. On the basis of 438.3 thousand lease agreements concluded between individuals, 503.4 billion soums of income tax were accrued. In comparison with 2023, the number of registered lease agreements increased by 13.3%, and the amount of accrued tax - by 4.5%.

On the basis of 167.7 thousand lease agreements concluded between legal entities, 296.1 billion soums of taxes were accrued. In comparison with 2023, the number of registered lease agreements increased by 15.7%, and the amount of accrued taxes - by 7.7%.

Property owners who rent out housing to students are exempt from paying tax on these incomes. In 2024, the amount of benefits applied by them amounted to 63.3 billion soums. 115.6 thousand housing rental agreements were signed with students. The total number of student tenants is 144,801 [1].

4. Features of the automated program "Online KKM", created for the purpose of obtaining online information about online KKM or virtual cash registers.

5. The automated program "Online Cash register" is a special solution developed for centralized collection, analysis and display of information about the operation of online cash registers (online cash registers) and virtual cash registers in real time. Its functionality is aimed at increasing the transparency of cash register equipment, monitoring compliance with legislation and promptly informing both government agencies and the business community. The main features of such a system are listed below;

6. Data collection and consolidation: The program aggregates information received from connected online cash registers and virtual cash registers, forming a single database. This allows you to get real-time information about completed operations, changes in the status of devices, and catalog them for further analysis.

Real-time monitoring: The system provides continuous monitoring of the operation of cash registers. Thanks to built-in dashboards and analytical dashboards, users can quickly see the current state of equipment, detect failures or deviations from standard operating modes, and quickly respond to possible violations.

Integration with state registers and accounting systems: The program is synchronized with official state registers of online sales registers, which allows you to ensure that devices meet the established requirements.

This integration facilitates automatic verification of the correct operation of CMCs, facilitates the procedure for registering them, and also helps tax authorities to obtain accurate and timely information about turnover.

Analytics and reporting: The collected data is processed using state-of-the-art analytical tools. Users get the opportunity to create detailed reports and summary statistics—from the total volume of operations to detailed monitoring of individual pieces of equipment, which helps both in operational control and in strategic planning.

Automated notifications and warnings: The program can generate automatic alerts about approaching critical deadlines, failures in the work of the CMC or other deviations from the norms, which allows you to take timely measures to eliminate malfunctions and prevent possible violations of the law.

Data security: The system has built-in modern information protection mechanisms – data encryption, access control, and digital signature. This ensures the safety of confidential information and compliance with regulatory requirements for information security.

Support for mobile and web interfaces: Access to the system can be provided through convenient web portals and mobile applications, which provides operational monitoring and management even in remote access conditions for representatives of government agencies and businesses.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Tax risk analysis is carried out in accordance with the regulation “On the procedure for tax risk management for identifying taxpayers (tax agents) with tax risk and classifying them according to the level of tax risk” approved by Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 dated 07.01.2021 “On Tax Risk Management, identification of Taxpayers (Tax agents) with tax risks, and about the organization and conduct of tax audits”

The Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan determines the strategy and tactics of the tax risk management system, collection and processing of information, analysis and assessment of tax risks, development and implementation of tax risk management measures.

In this regard, the following types of risk management systems should be applied by tax authorities:

- focus on areas of increased risk and ensure efficient use of available resources available to the tax authorities;
- increase the ability to detect tax violations;
- minimization of tax control in relation to taxpayers recognized as having a low tax risk by their type of activity;
- further expansion of the ability to detect tax violations, as well as taxpayers selected for tax audits, through an automated software product without the human factor;
- determining the forms of tax audits of taxpayers based on the level of tax risk.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.-89 “On amendments and additions to certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the adoption of the main directions of tax and budget policy for 2024”, dated 28.12.2023.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.-37 “On the State Program for the implementation of the Strategy” Uzbekistan — 2030 “in the” Year of Support for Youth and Business”, dated 21.02.2024.
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 150 “On approval of administrative regulations for the provision of certain public services in the field of registration of taxpayers” dated April 2, 2022
4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 320” On measures to further improve the activities of State tax Service bodies”, dated 17.04.2019.
5. D. G. Chernik. Taxes, Moscow: Finance and Statistics. 2002. - p. 38.
6. B. H. Aliyev Property taxation in Russia and abroad.\ Bulletin of Dagestan State University. 2012. Issue5
7. Buranova L.V., Sadikov I.G. (2025) Perspectives of reforming the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the conditions of globalization. Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot. №3. 2025. <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
8. Khudaykulov S.K., Buranova L.V. (2021) Classification and significance of factors affecting the financial power of the regions/ Scientific electronic magazine “Economy and innovative technologies”. No. 5, September-October, <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>
9. Fayzieva, M., Abdurakhmanova, G., Eshov, M., Khudoykulov, S., Kurbonov, S., Goyipnazarov, S., & Irmatova, A. (2023, December). The Role of Digital Development in the Reinforcement of the Government Social Protection System of Uzbekistan. In Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems (pp. 42-50). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3644713.3644720>
10. Zaitsev, A., Rodionov, D., Khudaykulov, S., Tuxliev, B., Stetsyunic, Y., Konnikov, E., & Dmitriev, N. (2023, December). Modeling the Impact of the Quality of the Political and Economic Environment on Population Migration. In Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems (pp. 139-156). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3644713.3644732>
11. https://buxgalter.uz/publish/doc/text205698_nalogi_vidy_stavki_sroki_otchetnosti_i_upl_aty111111#NalogVodRes08

12. Shodiev O.A. Excise tax in Uzbekistan: features and problems of modern development //Economics and Business: theory and practice. International monthly Scientific Journal, 2021, №5-3 (75)
13. Shodiev O. Excise taxation in Uzbekistan: general and special. International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences (IJRESS) Vol. 12 Issue 09 September- 2022.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 9

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>